

Lagrangian Extremization from Special Relativity?

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It is well known that a Lagrangian (usually kinetic energy - potential) may be extremized (subject to constraints) to obtain Newton's laws. In (1) it is argued that the Lagrangian is linked to Fisher's information and that there exists a general extremization process of Fisher's extremization subject to constraints i.e. Extreme Physical Information (EPI) which accounts for the Lagrangian process.

Here we note that special relativity yields $E^2 = p^2 + m^2$ ($c=1$) for a free particle and $(E-V)^2 = p^2 + m^2$ for one with a potential $V(x)$. From this follows Newton's conservation of energy equation $E = p^2/2m + V$. We thus ask: Does special relativity guarantee the existence of a function L (called a Lagrangian) such that its extremization leads to a dynamical equation of motion? We argue that it does. In particular, we argue that special relativity ensures $p = dL/dv$ if one defines L using the standard variable switch approach (used in thermodynamics) i.e. $E = -L + pv$. This, together with $v = dx/dt$, guarantees that the function L , when extremized, yields the equation of motion. Thus we argue that special relativity is behind the extremization/variational approaches of the Lagrangian and EPI.

Lagrangian Extremization

A Lagrangian $L(x,v,t)$ with $v = dx/dt$ is usually given by kinetic energy - potential energy + constraints with Lagrange multipliers. This combination may then be extremized to yield:

$$d/dt dL/dv - dL/dx + b_1 d/dx \text{ constraint}(x) \text{ ect} = 0 \quad ((1))$$

d/dt may then be converted to $v d/dx$ (if L is not a function of t explicitly) and an integration performed to obtain a conservation of energy equation. A question which arises is: Why should classical mechanics follow from a variational principle?

In (1) it is argued that the kinetic energy term is proportional to $dx/dt dx/dt$ which is of the form of Fisher's information. In general, it is argued that Fisher's information (which follows from statistics) may be extremized subject to constraints to yield not only classical mechanics, but also quantum mechanics. This approach is called extreme physical information or EPI.

We note, however, that special relativity yields an energy-momentum-potential equation with no need for extremization. Thus, we ask: Is it possible to show that special relativity guarantees an equivalent extremization approach? We consider this in the next two sections.

Special Relativity for a Free Particle

For a free particle, special relativity yields:

$$E^2 = p^2 + m^2 \quad (c=1, p=Ev) \quad ((2))$$

In the nonrelativistic limit this yields $E=pp/2m$. Thus no extremization process is needed. Nevertheless, there exists, both for the relativistic and nonrelativistic approaches, a function $L(x,v,t) = L(v)$ (for a free particle) which may be extremized to give the correct equation of motion:

$$L = \frac{1}{2}mv^2 \text{ (nonrelativistic) ((3a))} \quad \text{and} \quad L = -m_0c^2\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2} \text{ (relativistic) ((3b))}$$

We try to show that special relativity guarantees this result. We first consider the case of $E(p)$ being written in terms of a function $L(v)$ using a well-known approach used in thermodynamics e.g. $E(S,V)$ but F =free energy= $E-TS = F(T,V)$. Thus we define:

$$L = -E + pv \quad \text{in order that } L(v) \text{ and not a function of } p \text{ as } E \text{ is} \quad ((4))$$

We then note that:

$$d/dv (E - pv) = 0 \rightarrow dE/dv = p/E dp/dv = v dp/dv \text{ because } p=Ev. ((5))$$

$$\text{From ((4)) } dL/dv = dE/dv + p + v dp/dv \text{ so ((5)) yields: } dL/dv = p \quad ((6))$$

((6)) is a standard result from Lagrangian theory yet it follows directly from the definition ((4)) and special relativity. We argue that ((6)) is key in showing that special relativity leads to a function $L(v)$ (free particle) such that its extremization yields the equation of motion. P is a constant so $dp/dt=dp/dx=0$. $d/dt dL/dv$, however, is the form of an extremization of $L(v)$ so:

$$d/dt dL/dv \text{ (partial)} = 0 \quad ((7))$$

((7)) is the equation of motion, which follows from the extremization of $L(v)$ which in turn follows from special relativity.

Lagrangian with a Potential $V(x)$

In the case of a potential, the special relativistic result may be written as:

$$(E-V(x)) (E-V(x)) = pp + m_0c^2 \quad (c=1) \quad ((8)) \quad \text{with} \quad p = (E-V) v \quad ((9))$$

In the nonrelativistic limit, ((8)) yields the Newtonian result: $E = pp/2m$.

$$\text{Again one postulates: } L_1(v) = - (E-V) + pv \text{ or } E = -L_1(v) + V + pv \rightarrow E = -L(v,x) + pv \quad ((10))$$

where $L=L_1(v) - V$ with $L_1(v)$ being the free particle result.

Next, taking d/dv of ((8)) yields:

$$dE/dv = p/(E-V) dp/dv \text{ because } V(x). \text{ Then ((9)) implies that: } dE/dv = v dp/dv$$

From ((10)) one has $0 = -dL/dv \text{ (partial)} + p$ which is a standard Lagrangian theory result.

Thus: ((10)) becomes: $E = -L + v \text{ dL/dv (partial)}$ ((11))

$L(v,x) = L_1(v) + V(x)$ Next taking the full derivative d/dt of ((11)) yields:

$$0 = -dL/dx \text{ v} - dL/dv \text{ dv/dt} + dv/dt \text{ dL/dv} + v \text{ d/dv partial d/dv partial L} \text{ dv/dt}$$

Noting that: $d/dt \text{ dL/dv partial} = d/dv \text{ partial dL/dv partial} \text{ dv/dt}$ one finally has:

$$d/dt \text{ dL/dv partial} - dL/dx = 0 \text{ ((12))}$$

((12)) is of the form of an extremization equation, but one may note that this result follows from $p=dL/dv$ which is guaranteed through special relativity. Thus we argue that the extremization is really a consequence of special relativity.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that special relativity yields a relationship between E, p, m_0 for a free particle, namely $E^2 = p^2 + m_0^2 c^2$ ($c=1$). In the case of a potential $V(x)$, this becomes: $(E-V)^2 = p^2 + m_0^2 c^2$ ($c=1$). Thus no extremization approach is needed to arrive at this result. If one, however, considers the standard switching of variables method used in thermodynamics (e.g. $E(S,V) \rightarrow F(T,V)=E-TS$) then for $E(p,x)$ one may write: $E = -L(v) + pv$ for the free particle case. From $E^2 = p^2 + m_0^2 c^2$ with $p=Ev$ one has: $dE/dv = vdp/dv$ so $p = dL/dv \text{ partial}$ which is a standard Lagrangian result guaranteed solely from special relativity. Taking d/dt of $p=dL/dv$ shows that the equation of motion may be written as an extremization of L .

A similar argument holds in the case of a potential, but now $p = (E-V) v$. Nevertheless, special relativity again guarantees that $dL/dv \text{ partial} = p$. Taking d/dt (full derivative) of $E = -L + v dL/dv \text{ partial}$ where $L=L_1(v) - V(x)$, one may show that the equation of motion is again an extremization of L , i.e. $d/dt \text{ dL/dv partial} - dL/dx = 0$. This result, however, follows directly from special relativity which ensures that $p = dL/dv \text{ partial}$ together with $v=dx/dt$.

References

1. Chimento, L.P, and Pennini, F. and Plastino, A. The Frieden-Soffer Extreme Physical Information Principle in a Non-Extensive Setting (2012)
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